

Complexities In The Protection of Cultural Heritage In Non-International Armed Conflicts.

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Abstract

This paper elaborated about the applicability of the 1954 Hague Convention and its Second Protocol in protecting cultural heritage in armed conflicts of non-international character in Northern Mali. The two main critical applicability issues that hamper its enforcement will be discussed in referring to international humanitarian law. By using the Malian war, where the cultural heritage of Timbuktu was intentionally destroyed, the author will consider the extent to which these laws apply and create obligations in a national war context. The significance cultural heritage has requires ensuring the international law to be applied as broadly as possible, all belligerent groups and types of wars are compelled.

Keywords: Cultural Heritage; Non-International Armed Conflict; Mali; Timbuktu

Introduction

The protection of common cultural heritage has become subject of different branches of international law because of the relevance it has for humanity. The main legal instruments protecting cultural heritage during armed conflict are the 1954 Hague Convention and its two Additional Protocols. Furthermore, international humanitarian law (IHL) and international criminal law, have established some developments in the area. However, international law, as a form of soft law, generally lacks binding nature and enforcement mechanisms. This constitutes a great limitation for the protection of common cultural heritage during armed conflict, which is under threat nowadays. Trending events, such as the deliberate attack on the heritage in Timbuktu (Mali) during the ‘internal war’ that started in 2012, evidence the threat.

Moreover, the yet weak applicability of such international legislation becomes even more ambiguous when it comes to armed conflicts of non-international character. Contemporary wars, particularly space and actors involved, are considerably different from the international conflicts taking place when the Conventions were formed.

Ultimately, States are the ones expected to commit with the compliance of the Conventions, throughout investigations and prosecutions within their jurisdictions. Despite all these challenges, the ground-breaking Al Mahdi case, prosecuted by the ICC for destroying cultural property in Timbuktu, brings new avenues for fighting against impunity in the destruction of cultural heritage. Finally, the current ‘new wars’ context demonstrates the immediate need for the Convention to truly bind non-state actors and to apply to non-international armed conflicts (NIACs).

Subsequently, by means of a socio-political and legal analysis, this paper will argue that ‘the applicability of the 1954 Hague Convention and its Second Protocol in protecting cultural heritage in armed conflicts of non-international character is minimal and has significant weaknesses, as suggested in the case of the ‘internal war’ of Northern Mali and the destruction of Timbuktu.

The paper will start by giving a brief historical contextualization of the protection of cultural heritage under international law during armed conflict. After having introduced some international instruments, it will focus on the specific provisions of the 1954 Convention (Articles 18 and 19) and its Second Protocol (Article 22 and 3) that are relevant for NIACs. The two main critical applicability issues that hamper its enforcement will be discussed in referring to IHL. By using the Malian war, where the cultural heritage of Timbuktu was intentionally destroyed, the author will consider the extent to which these laws apply and create obligations in a national war context.

International Protection of Cultural Heritage

Since the Second World War, some international legal instruments that include the protection of cultural heritage during armed conflicts have been introduced. However, there is a clear lack of emphasis on conflicts of non-international character. The Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict (hereinafter the 1954 Hague Convention) and its two Additional Protocols (1954, 1999) represent the keystone regulations. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) is the international organization involved in the implementation and monitoring of such instruments.

Nonetheless, the historical context has shifted dramatically since the Conventions were drafted, leaving them outdated and scarcely effective. The key factor is the upsurge of new types of that break the old patterns of warfare upon which the law of armed conflict is constructed. Today, nearly every conflict worldwide is a NIAC, with non-state actors involved, as for instance the cases of Mali and Syria (Henckaerts, 1999). Nevertheless, the author does not ignore that the debate goes further, as these conflicts ‘while internal in nature, are highly ‘internationalised’’. This represents a considerable threat to cultural heritage protection as such conflicts potentially fall outside the scope of the Conventions regulations, which are mainly applicable to international conflicts.

The destruction resulting from the Second World War was the trigger for the 1954 Hague Convention and increased awareness of the relevance of cultural heritage for humankind. Nonetheless, there were previous historical developments starting with the Lieber Code (1863) and its Articles 35, 36 and 45, as well as the 1907 Hague Convention Concerning the Laws and Customs of War on Land in its Articles 27 and 56 and the 1907 Hague Convention IX in its Article 5 (Craig Forrest, 2011: 67).

The 1954 Hague Convention is the first international multilateral treaty exclusively directed to the protection of cultural property in times of armed conflict. Up to date, this most relevant instrument is only legally binding on the current 128 ratifying States.

Article 4 addresses the respect of cultural property in the event of armed conflict. The limitation of this Article is the determination of ‘event of armed conflict’ and the level of unrest or violence required. Moreover, the use of the term ‘respect’, despite the likely

vague obligation, must be understood as a 'legal restraint' that requires positive and negative duties. (Forrest, 2011: 79, 84). Scholars have argued that the terminology used often suggests 'responsibilities' rather than 'duties' (Brenner, 2006:262).

Through Article 18, the Convention initially extended the protection of cultural property during all armed conflicts by stating 'declared war or any other armed conflict' (Brenner, 2006: 242). Thus, the Article addresses the applicability in 'any other armed conflict' increasing the protection further than the traditional Clausewitzian understanding of declared wars, but lacks elucidating what an 'armed conflict' is (Odermatt, 2013: 19).

Whilst such expansion was an improvement at the time the Convention entered into force, it is not adequate for the current context. The Convention anticipated applicability issues as evidenced by the content of Article 19, which applies the Convention's content 'in the event of an armed conflict 'not of an international character'' (Howe, 2012: 414). The notion of 'not of an international character' is not spell out in the Convention and vaguely addressed in the Second Protocol.

This Article most likely applies to events described as 'civil war', or internal conflicts involving liberation movements, which remain imprecisely defined under international law and depend on political deliberations. While some scholars understand 'civil wars' as 'armed conflicts arising within states', others consider a requirement 'the level of a full-scale war' (Carrillo-Suárez, 1999:80). The attempt to define 'conflict' was abandoned during negotiations. The Second Protocol emerged in light of the events of Iran, Iraq, Kuwait and the Balkans wars. This led the International community to acknowledged the necessity of a Convention update, resulting in its Second Protocol (1999).

NIACs content is further developed in Article 22 of the Second Protocol. The Protocol's intention of elucidating the Convention was not the desired panacea. Events such as banditry, rebellions or certain forms of anarchy, would not fall under the regulations as Article 22(1) excluded 'situations of internal disturbances and tensions, such as riots, isolated and sporadic acts of violence and other acts of a similar nature' (Forrest, 2011: 84).

Moreover, the shortcoming of cultural heritage damaged in countries not party to the Convention remains, as 22(1) still requires events 'occurring within the territory of one of the Parties'. For instance, the Bamiyan Buddhas' destruction applicability is questionable since Afghanistan is not a party to the Convention.

Consequently, in defining the Protocol's scope of application, Article three extended its applicability to Article 18 (1)(2) of the Convention and Article 22(1) of the Protocol. Nonetheless, while 129 countries are High Contracting Parties of the Convention, only 73 have signed the Second Protocol. This means that only signatories of the Second Protocol are bound by Article 22.

Subsequently, there are two areas of concern about the applicability of the regulations, mainly caused by its vagueness. Firstly, the issue of internal conflicts as the war in Northern Mali. 'New wars' do not certainly fit in the international-internal dichotomy, and even if this was the case, internal wars are weakly regulated.

As a party to the Second Protocol, NIACs scope of applicability is limited to some internal conflicts. It does not apply to internal disturbances that do not meet the definition of 'armed conflict'. It makes susceptible to different interpretation when an internal disturbance or liberation movement evolves into an armed conflict, such as it occurred in Syria. Jean Pictet's commentary to common Article III to the Geneva Convention

contributed with a useful rubric for distinguishing ‘armed conflicts’ from internal disturbances (Howe, 2012: 419).

Under international case-law of the International Criminal Court for Former Yugoslavia (ICCFY), armed conflicts ‘are protracted armed confrontations occurring between governmental armed forces and the forces of one or more armed groups, or between such groups arising on the territory of a State’. See *Prosecutor v. Dusko Tadic (Judgement on Sentencing Appeal)*, (International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia, Appeals Chamber, Case No IT-94-1-A, 15 July 1999) [70]. The armed confrontation must reach a minimum level of intensity and the parties involved must show a minimum level of organisation. It was also required by the ICCFY for both elements to be independently satisfied. Such requirement resulted in delaying almost a year the recognition of the situation in Syria as a NIAC and thus, the trigger of IHL protection with all the drawbacks that would entail. ‘Low-intensity’ and asymmetric warfare, such as the cases of Mexico and Colombia, may not fall within the threshold of ‘conflicts of a certain degree of intensity’ despite the gravity of such conflicts (Odermatt, 2013: 20).

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